

The GA4GH Genomic Knowledge Standards for Variant Interpretation

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Abstract

Most observed genetic variants are of uncertain significance, largely due to technical barriers to the precise sharing of knowledge about them. Addressing this challenge, the GA4GH Genomic Knowledge Standards (GKS) Work Stream develops interoperable standards for

variant representation and annotation through collaboration among a multinational network of stakeholders. These standards deliver “AI-Ready data”: information that carries explicit meaning as defined through formal vocabularies, ontologies, and machine-readable data schemas that can empower agentic reasoning on complex genomic knowledge. The GKS Work Stream develops and maintains the Variant Representation Specification (VRS), Categorical Variant Representation Specification (Cat-VRS), and Variant Annotation Specification (VA-Spec) to enable consistent and computable exchange of variant knowledge across clinical, industrial, and research institutions.

Main Text

Interpreting rare genetic variants depends on sharing genomic evidence across institutions and studies. While extensive data repositories have been generated, effective use of these data has been hindered by a lack of strategies for effective data sharing¹. The GA4GH Genomic Knowledge Standards (GKS) Work Stream has developed a set of integrated data standards for describing, categorizing, and annotating genetic variants, with structured, machine-readable specifications to facilitate the scalable sharing of variant interpretation knowledge that is readily *interpretable, computable, and reusable* ([Fig. 1](#)).

The Variant Representation Specification (VRS)^{2,3} provides a computable framework to serve as a *lingua franca* for federated and interoperable variant representation. VRS defines precise data models and computed identifier conventions that allow identical variants to be represented unambiguously across reference sequence contexts. Its structured framework includes the *variant type* (including simple alleles, copy-number changes, and structural variants), the *reference sequence* (as specified in the GA4GH refget standard⁴), and the *location* of the variant on the reference. Importantly, its unique, unambiguous variant identifiers, derived as digest hashes of the variant within a normalized reference-sequence context, enable efficient and reproducible identification of known variants. The VRS reference implementation supports interoperability with other variant data standards, including HGVS⁵ and VCF⁶. While each of these standards includes conventions tailored to their respective applications, VRS complements them by focusing on self-contained variant representation and conventions that prioritize variant searching, bridging simple and complex variant representation with common data structures.

The Categorical Variant Representation Specification (Cat-VRS)⁷ builds on VRS to describe sets of variants that share biologically or clinically meaningful properties, such as variants that result in the same function within a genomic location or gene fusions arising from multiple potential breakpoints. It represents these concepts through two components: *Constraints*, properties that must be met for a variant to be a member of a given category, and *Recipes*, sets of constraints that collectively define commonly-used groupings of distinct variants. This model

allows for novel variants to be matched against known categories at scale, extending existing knowledge to newly observed variants.

The Variant Annotation Specification (VA-Spec) provides a logical, semantically-precise framework for representing the classification of evidence lines, evidence records, and supporting provenance records. This standard is built around several core objects for representing a knowledge assertion, referred to as a *Statement*; one or more *Evidence Lines* (such as ACMG/AMP evidence codes) that support the *Statement*; and one or more *Study Results*, representing the experimental observations contributing to those *Evidence Lines*. The standard also includes *Method*, *Contributor*, *Agent*, and *Document* provenance objects that describe how, when, and by whom those observations were generated, and where they were published or disseminated. By combining these evidence and provenance records with a *Statement*, VA-Spec enables greater reproducibility in variant assessment.

Major genomics initiatives, including ClinGen⁸, gnomAD⁹, and the VICC¹⁰, are now sharing variant knowledge via the GKS standards, while data consumers including Epic Systems and Elimu Informatics are leveraging these data to infer new knowledge.

The development of these standards is driven by the adopter's stated needs (**Figure 1**). Data consumers, tool developers, and other interested parties regularly engage with GKS through public avenues, including:

- *Hackathons*: semi-annual community-driven collaborative events bringing together adopters, developers, and domain experts to advance standards development, prototype implementations, address interoperability challenges, and establish priorities for future work.
- *Think Tanks*: monthly forums and mini-hackathons that provide ongoing adopter support, facilitate discussion of implementation challenges and emerging use cases, and serve as an accessible entry point for new community members.
- *Open House meetings*: quarterly introductions to GKS products and collaboration aimed at the general public. These alternate between Asia-Pacific- and European-friendly time zones to foster international engagement.

The GA4GH community welcomes anyone with an interest to get involved in these activities. See https://www.ga4gh.org/work_stream/genomic-knowledge-standards/ for more information.

Fig. 1: The Variant Interpretation standards of the GA4GH Genomic Knowledge Standards Work Stream. This Venn diagram describes the forms of data or knowledge conveyed by Variant Representation Specification (VRS), Categorical Variant Representation Specification (Cat-VRS), and Variant Annotation Specification (VA-Spec). At the intersections are some of the major resources that now leverage each standard.

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